

This review analyses the scholarly literature on peer review, which assess its suitability and relevance as an evaluative system for discerning academic quality, asking whether peer review provides an objective evaluation of scholarly output or whether it is intrinsically flawed. Various biases such as the Matthew effect (Smith 2006), the Hawthorn effect (Bornmann 2012), are identified in the literature, as well as differences in peer review across disciplines. This review will examine how Mertonian norms of science: communalism, universalism, disinterestedness, and organised scepticism, have prevailed in critiques of peer review and how these norms serve as guides in effort to review the process (Souder 2011). Despite its many inherent flaws, many scholars, according to Potvin, have viewed peer-review in a similar manner to Churchill's view of democracy: "the worst form of government except for all those other forms..." (qtd. in Potvin 2017) This review will begin with Spier's account of the origins of peer-review in the 1700s, assessing how the peer review process developed over time and analyse how changes in scholarship, technology and society have shaped the peer-review process over time.

Spier (2002) provides a historical account of the peer-review process, locating its origins in the Royal Society of London for Improving Natural Knowledge and their decision in 1752 to adopt a procedure akin to that of the Royal Society of Edinburgh where communications sent for publication in their journal *Philosophical Transactions* would be subject to appraisal by a select group of members knowledgeable in that field who would advise the editor on how the material should progress. Spier relates how advances in technology helped to shape the peer-review process in the succeeding period. In the nineteenth century due to the laboriousness of copying manuscripts, evaluation of scholarly output often rested with the editor of a journal. This changed with the arrival of the typewriter in the 1890s, allowing carbon copies of a document to be made which could then be shared

by a committee. In the twentieth century, the advent of the Xerox machine provided an efficient means of copying articles for peer evaluation. Journal editors presented with a greater “diversity and specialisation of material” (Spier 2002, p.358) began to seek guidance outside of the sponsoring society. The rise of scholarly scientific output seeking publication grew dramatically during the twentieth century, and where editors had previously struggled to fill journal space, this new abundance of scientific scholarly material available meant that journals became more discriminatory in what they published (Spier, 2002).

The centrality of peer review in scientific advancement has been defended throughout the twentieth century and more recently in the twenty-first century. Ziman (1968) contended that the referee is “the lynchpin about which the whole business of Science is pivoted”, arguing that publication in a peer-reviewed journal confers “the *imprimatur* of scientific authenticity” on an article (p.148). Shatz (2004) also defended the positive impact of peer review on scholarship, arguing that it “motivates scholars to produce their best, provides feedback that substantially improves work that is submitted and enables scholars to identify products that will find worth reading” (p.30). However, commentators have also recognised the potential for bias in this system, which has constituted “probably the most frequently voiced concern about the peer review system” (Shatz p.36). Smith (2006) in an article for the *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine* questions the purpose of peer review, attempting to establish evidence for its existence away from its status as conferring a publication as “blessed” (p.178). He argues that it is impossible to come up with a definition of peer review on “operational terms” (p.178) and that ironically its continued existence in scientific publications seems to come down to belief. Smith (2006) identifies that in a system based on trust, there are various biases which make peer-review a “system full of problems” (p.178) including reputational bias against scholarly output from lesser-known researchers and institutions (the Matthew effect) and a bias in medical scholarly publishing against negative

studies. Smith questions how objectivity can be obtained in both reviewer and process. In questioning the objectivity of a reviewer, Smith asks that by appointing someone with appropriate specialist knowledge of the same research area “he or she is probably a direct competitor?” (p.178). Objectivity in the process itself is undermined by the arbitrary nature of how it manifests across journals, disciplines and editors where it ranges from a cursory “It looks alright to me” to “somebody pouring all over the paper, asking for raw data, repeating analyses, checking all the references, and making detailed suggestions for improvement?” (Smith 2006, p.178). Bornmann (2012) identifies the “Hawthorne effect” in journal peer review as a phenomenon where the assessment of the same manuscript differs across journals, indicating that a manuscript is rated by editorial teams not on its merits alone but according to “journal specific factors” (p.859) with many rejected papers being taken up for publication elsewhere. The increasing pressure to publish, as an “evaluative measure of scientific performance” (Bornmann 2012, p.860) has probably fuelled this process, where authors send less than optimal work to more prestigious journals first, where they are inevitably rejected and where editors at these journals are inundated with submissions “leading in many cases to more rejections, appeals and complaints about the system overall” (McCook 2006, p.26)

The “canonisation of peer review” is also challenged by Potvin (2017), where she attempts to shine a light on what is an often secretive process, shrouded in academic mystery, examining the role of the reviewer, “typically constrained by the peer review systems in which they play a part” and “guided by explicit requirements and unwritten norms of scholarly subcultures.” (p.734). Potvin (2017) examines how the term peer-review can be applied to a process with little or no standardisation but which is led by local, often hidden agendas and criticism of which also takes place away from public view. She cites research by Weller who observed in a comprehensive study that there is no definition of peer review

as it differs according to discipline, journal, and editorship. This lack of specificity of what constitutes peer-review has impeded its critical appraisal within academia and “lays the groundwork for clumsy critiques of peer review, which generalize from specific applications and then make the case not for an overhaul of the system, but for adjustment and even extension of particular practices or implementations—that is, for more or different peer review” (p.735). Potvin cites efforts in the Digital Humanities to make the review process more open, where for example reviewers can view other reviewers’ comments, as a way of establishing greater courtesy and accountability in how they review research. Potvin underscores the significance of this occurring in a cross-disciplinary field like the Digital Humanities where, as Lamont (2009) remarks, there is competition over “whose criteria gets universalised as disciplinary criteria”. The multidisciplinary scope of this field further challenges the notion of who is qualified as a peer to assess research output, particularly when promotion has traditionally relied on publication output.

Souder (2011) argues that suggestions for the reform of the peer-review system are “guided by whether conscious or not [are] the Mertonian norms of science (augmented by Ziman)” and he sets about a systematic evaluation of the literature through these categories. Merton (1942) outlined four norms of science: communalism, universalism, disinterestedness, organised scepticism; Ziman augmented this list with the norm of originality (Souder 2011). However, Ziman (2000) cautions that “norms only affirm ideals; they do not describe realities. They function precisely to resist contrary impulses” (p.31) Furthermore Ziman (2000) asserts that “It would make no sense to insist, for example, on ‘universalism’, if ‘particularism’ were not a tempting alternative” and that by “assuming general virtue, they open opportunities for the unscrupulous” (p.31). Souder contends that though approval by a process of review is a good measure of a paper’s integrity, ultimate approval comes post-publication when the work is reviewed by a wider body of researchers,

serving to underline for all involved in peer-review that they “must work toward belief that has been challenged, not toward faith that must be obeyed.” (p58). Guetzkow et al. (2004) analyse how disciplinary variation impacts the way originality is viewed by research panellists. They also draw on Merton’s influential work *The Sociology of Science*, in formulating an approach to the place of originality in knowledge creation: “it is through originality, in greater or smaller increments, that knowledge advances” (Merton 1973 [1957]:293). They perform a comparative evaluation of how originality is perceived in scholarship across disciplines – namely the humanities, history, and social sciences. Through content analysis of interviews with those involved in funding panels in these disciplines, a differing idea of what is considered original in these disciplines emerges. For example, in the humanities and history, originality of approach is considered important; whereas originality of method is considered important in the social sciences. Though the impact of substantive issues differed across disciplines, non-substantive issues were shown to feature similarly across these disciplines including how positive moral qualities such as bravery, passion or conviction had a desirable impact on evaluation. Undesirable character traits including laziness, conformity as well as slavish attempts to be intellectually trendy had a negative impact on evaluation. Guetzkow et al. (2004) link this emphasis on an author’s character to the search by panellists for authenticity in scholarship, bestowing approval on those scholars who display the balancing act necessary to navigate the “Scylla and Charybdis of academic life: avoiding a reproduction of the *status quo* while steering clear of the latest intellectual trends.” (p.204). Guetzkow et al. argue that by adopting the natural sciences as a “normative model” has created an “artificial levelling” of theoretical cultures in other disciplines, particularly in social science. They argue that in seeking to adhere to Mertonian norms of universalism in all disciplines, ignores the centrality of how non-substantive qualities such as character are valued in disciplines such as the humanities. Instead they argue that to enhance

research and peer evaluation it important to acknowledge “the diverse forms that originality takes” (Guetzkow et al. 2004, p.206).

The expectation that Mertonian “disinterestedness” prevails in peer review has been challenged by critics such as Smith (2006) who point to the potential for competition and rivalry inherent in the nature of a peer: “he or she is probably a direct competitor?”. Merton (1942:1973) espoused the norm of universalism on the grounds that “To restrict scientific careers on grounds of other than lack of competence is to prejudice the furtherance of knowledge” (p.272) but its prevalence in scholarship is contested by critics who argue still that scholarly output is disadvantaged based on factors (conscious or otherwise) based on age, gender and supporting institution have been observed to bias reviewers (Travis & Collins 1991 ; Rittman & Classen 2015). Responses to mitigate threats to these norms include the double-blind peer-review where as well as the reviewer’s identity being concealed from the author, author and institution are also concealed from the reviewer. There has been criticism of this approach including Smith (2006) who argues that it is difficult to truly conceal a author’s identity, even without their name, due to clues, such as the area of study or inclusion of references to their own work. Blank (1991) carried out a randomized experiment at the American Economic Review to assess the impact of single-blind and double-blind peer-review on publication and found that when papers were double-blind reviewed, fewer papers were accepted and reviewer comments were more critical. Blank (1991) rejects the notion that is always possible to guess an author’s identity, stating that while this happens to some degree, more than half remain truly blind. Spier (2002) adds that double-blind peer reviews produced “more extensive and thoughtful comments” from reviewers (Innovation p.101). Rittman and Classen (2015) outline their decision to adopt a double-blind policy at their journal *Humanities* stating that while no system is perfect, they “believe that this decision will reduce bias and particularly help emerging scholars to receive a fair review”. Their

decision is an attempt to mitigate as much as possible the role of biases “ranging from the unconscious to the blatant prejudice” (Rittman and Classen 2015) in the peer-review process and aligns with the principle of disinterestedness outlined by Merton.

Squazzoni (2019) defends the merits of peer review in a blog article for the LSE. He asserts that peer review is often mistakenly portrayed as simply an objective test of the quality of a research paper but that this view ignores the role of peer review as “simultaneously a context in which experts develop, adapt and enforce standards of judgement, a form of (direct and indirect) connection and cooperation, a disciplined, mediated discourse between (often unrelated) experts in a “safe” (though often disorganised and ambiguous) environment” (LSE Blog). Squazzoni and his team at PEERE studied rejected manuscripts and discovered that those which eventually were published by other journals benefitted in terms of the exposure they gained through successive rounds of peer review, a factor measured through increased citation. He argues that peer review can be a value multiplier when detailed reviews and review disagreement are considered and notes that some articles were subsequently published by journals with a higher journal impact factor. Another positive aspect for authors shown in this study was that peer-review enhanced scientific collaboration, with “referees collaborating directly with authors they previously reviewed, whom they were not previously related with” (Squazzoni 2019). Squazzoni refers to this as the “invisible hand of peer review” and argues that bias in peer review “lies not in the subjectivity of expert judgement but the lack of diversity and representativeness in referee selection” (LSE Blog). Shatz (2004) concedes that bias can exist in peer review, in positive and negative ways for the author. He terms positive bias “the halo effect” where an article of lesser quality is upwardly appraised (Shatz 2004, p.36). Gorman (2007) dubbed one such positive bias the “Oppenheim effect” where editorial decision to publish an article is not based on its quality but on the author’s reputation.

The SpotOn Report (2017) looked to the future of peer review, which “presents one of the greatest opportunities, and challenges in advancing discovery” outlining whilst advances have been made, “truly transformative change has not been made” (p.2). One such attempt to bring about transformative change, as outlined in the report, lies in preprints. One negative consequence of delays in the peer review process is found in scientific collaboration, meaning that by the time findings are published research is often out of date, causing frustration for scientists (Spot-on Report 2017). As one post-doctoral scientist puts it in this report: “No one would read the news with months of delay, but that’s what we scientists do” (Spot-on Report 2017, p.7). One way of bypassing this delay is by uploading scientific papers to pre-print servers such as bioRxiv. Many papers uploaded to this server are subsequently published in journals post peer-review but access findings to findings can take place before this happens. Some see a greater adoption of preprints in research dissemination as a threat to the system of peer review (Spot-on Report 2017). However Pulverer (2016) suggests it takes pressure from researchers to publish and means that journals can invest “time and effort to add reliability and reproducibility assurances to research findings through careful peer review and prepublication quality control and curation processes” (EMBO Journal).

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